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CYBERSECURITY IN THE FIELD OF IOT TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. The impact of the growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) on cybersecurity is analyzed, threats and challenges arising in this regard are identified, and strategies for ensuring security in the IoT ecosystem are proposed. Technical and organizational measures to ensure cybersecurity are analyzed, including data encryption, authorization and authentication, protection against unauthorized access and monitoring of devices. Aspects of cooperation between manufacturers, operators and users of IoT devices to ensure cybersecurity are also considered.

Keywords: Cybersecurity, IOT, confidentiality, Integrity, usability, authentication, authorization

INTRODUCTION

Cybersecurity in the field of the Internet of Things (IoT) is becoming increasingly important with the increase in the number of connected devices. IoT technology provides huge advantages in various industries, but it also poses serious security threats, as it increases the attack surface for intruders.

cyber attacks. The unreliable security of IoT devices also poses a threat to privacy and data security, which is an important aspect of the impact of IoT growth.

Thus, the impact of the growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) covers both positive and negative aspects, and requires an integrated approach to ensure the security and protection of important data.

One of the main problems in the field of IoT cybersecurity is the lack of security standards. Many devices are designed with insufficient attention to security, which makes them vulnerable to cyber attacks. Insufficient protection of confidential data also poses a serious threat to users of IoT devices.

Technical and organizational measures to ensure cybersecurity include various aspects, such as:

Data encryption: Protection of confidential information by converting it into an unreadable format using cryptographic algorithms.

Authorization and Authentication: Establishing and verifying the identity of users and devices to prevent unauthorized access to systems and data.

Unauthorized access protection: Implementation of access control mechanisms and privilege restrictions to prevent unauthorized access to systems and data.

Device Monitoring: Continuous monitoring of device and network activity to detect suspicious or abnormal activity indicating possible cyber threats.

Organizational measures include organizational security policy, employee training, development of security standards and risk management.

Technical and organizational measures to ensure cybersecurity play a critical role in preventing and detecting cyber threats, as well as in protecting confidential data and ensuring the security of information systems and devices.

To ensure cybersecurity in the field of IoT, it is necessary to apply an integrated approach, including data encryption, authorization and authentication of devices, protection against unauthorized access, monitoring and analysis of events, as well as software and firmware updates.

IoT security also requires collaboration between device manufacturers, operators, and users. Manufacturers should pay more attention to security issues when developing devices, and operators and users should be aware of security methods and follow best security to assure the security of their devices and data.

In general, ensuring cybersecurity in the field of IoT is a complex and multifaceted task that requires joint efforts from manufacturers, operators and users. Improving security standards, sharing threat information, and continuously updating technologies and practices are critical to overcoming cybersecurity challenges in the field of IoT.

In recent years, the Internet of Things has become an integral part of our daily lives, and organizations are increasingly using IoT technologies to increase efficiency and improve user experience. However, with the increase in the number of devices connected to the Internet, the risk of cyber-attacks increases, which can lead to serious consequences. In this article, we will look at the main aspects of cybersecurity in the field of IoT technology.

Initially, cybersecurity in the field of IoT technology should begin with the design of devices. Developers should take into account the features of IoT and create devices with security in all aspects: from hardware to software. For example, developers should use cryptography to protect data, manage access to devices using passwords, authentication and authorization.

A number of well-known manufacturers already have examples of devices that have been attacked and used as "botnets". Devices can become victims of cyber attacks when using devices with weak passwords or devices that are not protected by antiviruses.

In addition, how the devices will connect to the Internet and interact with each other also depends on how secure they will be in use. It is important that the devices are protected from buffer overflow or SQL injection attacks.

The next important aspect of cybersecurity in the field of IoT technology is the security of computer networks. As a rule, devices on the network are connected to a common Internet access point, which means that any unauthorized access to the network can lead to data leakage or hacking of devices. Therefore, it is important to use secure connections and security protocols such as WPA2 and SSL to prevent unauthorized access to devices and networks.

Another important point is protection against physical cyber attacks. It seems that a loaded or missing intercom is a simple flaw, but it can also be a vulnerability to hacking and weakening the security of the device. In addition, a ban on physical access to the device can make it more protected from hacking or malware installation.

Interaction between devices in an IoT network can be complex and require processing a large amount of data. This means that data processing must be provided with a high degree of security, including encryption of all transmitted data, as well as protection against unauthorized access. It is also necessary to set access rules for individual applications and devices.

In addition, devices should have their own systems for monitoring and countering cyber attacks, which include detecting unusual activity and immediately notifying network administrators. Detection and registration of all unusual activities is one of the main methods of ensuring security in IoT networks.

Aspects of cooperation between manufacturers, operators and users of IoT devices to ensure cybersecurity:

The role of manufacturers: Discuss the importance of implementing security at the IoT device development level, including the use of encryption, authentication mechanisms, and security updates.

The role of operators: Consider the measures that operators can take to ensure the security of IoT devices on their networks, including monitoring activity, updating software and providing training to users.

User Role: Discuss the importance of user awareness and education about the basics of cybersecurity, including strong password rules, regular updates, and awareness of potential threats.

Finally, it is important to understand that cybersecurity is not a static process, so it is necessary to regularly test the security of devices and increase security measures. This should include checking

vulnerabilities and security issues using automated scanners, as well as analyzing logging systems to detect unusual activity.

In conclusion, cybersecurity in the field of IoT technology is a serious problem that requires comprehensive security measures for devices, networks and the data they process. Many companies, including device manufacturers, should devote more resources and attention to security in IoT technologies. Security should be integrated into every step of device development, production and operation to ensure protection against cyber attacks, data leaks and other threats in the field of IoT technology.

Cybersecurity in the field of IoT technology requires joint efforts on the part of manufacturers, operators and users. Effective cooperation between these parties is key to ensuring the security of IoT devices and preventing cyber threats.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to pay more attention to the integration of security measures at the design level, the development of security standards for IoT devices, regular software updates, as well as training users about the basics of cybersecurity.

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